
Waterside Academy: Let's Paddle for Positive Change

Impact Report

Canal & River Trust with
Waterside Academy

Waterside Academy: Let's Paddle for Positive Change Impact Report

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FOREWORD

“Waterside Academy: Let's Paddle for Positive Change has been a powerful example of what can happen when local partners come together around a shared vision. Through our partnership with Waterside Academy and GroundsWell, we have helped open up access to the Leeds & Liverpool Canal, enabling some of the region's most vulnerable young people to experience the benefits of spending time on and alongside the water.

What makes this project particularly special is its focus on creating lasting change. By training school staff, improving access to the canal, and embedding paddlesport within the school's offer, the programme has created a sustainable legacy that will continue to benefit young people long after the initial project has ended.

”

JON HORSFALL
CANAL & RIVER TRUST

“Waterside Academy: Let's Paddle for Positive Change, delivered with the Canal & River Trust and Sefton's Waterside Academy, offered a unique chance to strengthen an existing community partnership while improving access to a local urban green and blue space, the canal. Paddlesport and canal-side activities gave staff new ways to engage students in a calm, low-pressure setting, supporting learning, connection, and wellbeing.

Designed with sustainability and growth in mind, the project's train-the-trainer approach, alongside development of a local paddle hub, has created lasting impact, generating positive ripple effects beyond the school and into the wider community.

”

SARAH RODGERS
UNIVERSITY OF LIVERPOOL

CANAL & RIVER TRUST

Canal & River Trust is a charity that cares for 2,000 miles of a 200-year-old network of canals, rivers, reservoirs, and docks, connecting many of the UK's urban and rural areas. Its vision is to transform places and enrich lives. "Let's" is our national participatory campaign; free and local programmes focused on physical, health, and wellbeing activities. Our goal is to embed these activities into the community, growing them into a sustainable offer where local organisations are trained to deliver the programmes themselves.

Learn more about the Canal and River Trust [here](#)

GROUNDSWELL

The GroundsWell Consortium is a team of researchers, local communities, implementers and policymakers who aim to better understand and evidence the role of **green and blue spaces** within wider social, economic, environmental, cultural and health systems. GroundsWell's research activity is based in Edinburgh, Liverpool and Belfast, where it is being led by researchers at Queen's University Belfast.

A key aim of GroundsWell is to encourage, enable, and collaborate on community-engagement and community-led research. To facilitate this, GroundsWell launched a **Community Innovation Fund** programme, where community organisations could be supported in implementing programmes and evaluating impact.

Learn more about the GroundsWell Community Innovation fund [here](#)

LET'S PADDLE FOR POSITIVE CHANGE

Waterside Academy: Let's Paddle for Positive Change is a collaborative initiative between Canal & River Trust (the Trust) and Waterside Academy (Waterside), Sefton Council's pupil referral unit. The project aimed to explore and harness the potential of urban green and blue spaces, specifically the Trust's waterways, to enhance the physical and mental wellbeing of young people whose needs are not being met in mainstream education. Using a train-the-trainer approach, the project supported staff and students to grow together, delivering a paddlesport programme on the canal adjacent to Waterside.

Partnering with Waterside Academy

Waterside Academy provides an educational environment for young people who have had previous or ongoing barriers to learning in mainstream settings. Staff provide personalised support to help students build resilience and confidence, using alternative strategies and enrichment activities alongside academic learning. The campus, located in South Sefton, Merseyside, runs adjacent to the Liverpool Leeds Canal.

The project leveraged an existing partnership between the Trust and the school, Previous attempts to provide paddlesport activities on site faced infrastructure and access barriers and required substantial time resources from Trust staff. Additionally, the unique delivery model excluded the programme from typical funding sources.

TIMELINE OF ACTIVITIES AND WHO TOOK PART

55 students participated in paddlesport activities

6 school staff trained as Paddle UK Paddlesport Instructors

15 new paddle craft on site at Waterside Academy

*At taster sessions, students and staff chose:
4 canoes,
4 sit-on kayaks,
3 closed kayaks and
4 stand-up paddle boards (SUPs)*

March 2024

- Vegetation management at the canal access point
- Accessible gate installed from the school to the canal

April to May

- Staff paddlesport instructor training began
- Trust-led paddlesport taster sessions with pupils and staff to choose paddle crafts to purchase

July

- Staff paddlesport instructor assessment (all 6 staff qualify as Paddle UK paddlesport Instructors)

September

- Trust paddlesport refresher session for staff

September to March 2025

- Trust-led paddle programme with students

March 2025

- Additional £4000 secured by school to install a mobile, outdoor education cabin
- Transition to school-led paddlesport delivery

EVALUATION PROCESS

Canal & River Trust and GroundsWell researchers worked together to co-develop an evaluation approach that captured the information most useful to the Trust and Waterside.

Semi-structured interviews with staff, alongside student focus groups, were used to understand experiences and outcomes. The findings were then analysed thematically to identify key patterns and insights.

Initial findings are presented in this report, with a further publication planned to explore the wider learning and outcomes from the project, including opportunities to scale this approach within the local community and in other areas.

THEORY OF CHANGE

The theory of change sets out how the project's activities are expected to lead to meaningful outcomes for young people, staff, and the wider community.

By improving access to the canal and building staff confidence to deliver paddlesport, the project creates the conditions for increased participation, skill development, and stronger connections to place. Over time, this contributes to sustained engagement, improved wellbeing, and a lasting local legacy.

IMPACTS ON STUDENTS

A DIFFERENT KID ON THE WATER

Students' behaviour and demeanour transformed while on the water. This was related to the calm environment on the canal, perceived and real fear, and undertaking a new activity.

“ *As soon as you sort of release them from the gate, they literally turn into different kids.*

[The students'] physical stance go from being quite stressed, quite tense, to soften, to loosen.

[The group was] loud, very boisterous, bouncy, physically moving constantly. That wasn't what they did on the water. They were so mellow. It was calm. They laughed and talked...they talked differently.

”

EMBRACING RISK AND ADVENTURE

Students' confidence and behaviour benefited from embracing risk in a safe setting. This was rooted in a perceived and real risk of falling in, and also 'losing face' if they failed at something new.

“ *Their behaviour is going to potentially affect them falling in and getting wet, so then they are more happy to act a bit more mature.*

I think one of the biggest barriers is the children's self-confidence and being vulnerable. They're [afraid of feeling foolish] if they can't get on the first time, or they wobble, or they fall in.

A few [students] may be a bit scared thinking they're going to fall in, but...getting out of the comfort zone, that's what you're trying to do, encourage them to get out of their comfort zone as much as possible. It's a positive outcome, isn't it?

”

IMPACTS ON STUDENTS

ENABLED RELATIONSHIP BUILDING

Canal-based activities enabled student and staff interactions that led to positive relationship building. This is related to the linear nature of the canal, being outdoors and the low-pressure environment.

“ We can actually go and sit out in nature whilst we're doing our conversation. For some students, I think that will make a massive difference. Being able to sit in the nice weather, surrounded by nature, safely.

[The student] needs one-to-one, that's how his relationships form, like sort of linear communication, one-to-one, he's in his element.

We recently did work around trauma-informed [practices]... sitting side-by-side is actually less threatening. One of the first things you do in a kayak or a canoe is, you're side by side, and you see them sort of going up and down the canal next to each other, and lots of the conversations – staff come and say, “Oh, I had a really good chat.”

”

IMPACTS ON STAFF

ANOTHER TOOL IN THE TOOLBOX

The paddlesport training, programme and the improved access to the canal gave staff new skills and opportunities to engage and work with the students.

“ *Classrooms aren't for everyone, and they aren't for all of our kids in particular, and we know that's some of the issues that they have in school, so we want to offer something different.* ”

It's helped me engage pupils here, so it's almost given me another tool in my belt and another way to build a relationship up with pupils here. ”

IMPROVED STAFF WELLBEING

Staff shared that undertaking canal activities generally enhanced their own wellbeing and experience of doing their job. This was related to being in a calm, outdoor environment and positive interactions with students.

“ *It's probably the best part of my week.* ”

The majority of the time, I got off [the water] feeling as though the young people had achieved something, they'd got something out of it that they wouldn't normally get...it uplifted me. ”

IMPACTS ON SCHOOL AND COMMUNITY

SHAPED SCHOOL IDENTITY

The project supported a shift in the identity of the school which is ongoing. This is related to shifts in internal and community perceptions of the school and the new *Waterside* name.

“ *The paddlesport, the canal stuff is part of the package. And it's almost we've built our identity on it a bit as well, haven't we.*

If people were to come and see that this is the kind of thing that we're trying to do for our pupils, and we want you to be part of it, that reputation change would be massive for our kids.

”

TRANSFORMED PERCEPTION OF THE CANAL

General perceptions and attitudes towards the canal were changed for the positive as a result of direct experience with canal activities.

“ *Staff and pupils were thinking...[the] canal is dirty, I don't want to get in there...but then once they're in, you know, they're loving it.*

When you actually get on the canal...it's [anti social behaviour is] not as prominent as what you think it is going to be. So I do think my opinion on this part of the canal in particular has definitely changed.

It's now somewhere that, if I was to have kids of my own, that I'd be thinking, yeah, let's go there. It's a nice space, it's open, it's fresh, it's inviting.

”

WHAT MADE IT WORK

There were many elements that came together to make this programme work. Central to all of these, were three core components:

- 1 Flexibility and openness of the school to pilot such a unique project
- 2 Ability to adapt delivery and training to the often changing needs and environment of the school
- 3 A school staff project champion and committed delivery partner driving the programme forward

TO GET IT UP AND RUNNING:

- Committed and engaged school staff to undertake the rigorous paddlesport instructor training and organise paddlesport delivery
- Flexible and attuned training delivery partner
- Ease of access to the canal and equipment
- Built initial delivery capacity with Trust staff to engage students and launch activities
- Supportive hand-over period for school staff to begin to manage delivery on their own

TO GET STUDENTS ON THE WATER:

- External staff who know how to meet the needs of students (e.g., encouraging without pushing)
- Giving options and choices to students (e.g., through the type of paddle craft).
- Seeing their friends and peers on the water
- Appropriate clothing for paddlesport

TO SUSTAIN DELIVERY AND IMPACT:

- Training school staff ensured delivery continued after Trust staff left
- Realising the full potential and other uses of the canal and embedding this in school curriculum
- Sharing resources with the community in the form of the paddlesport hub

GOING FORWARD: SUSTAINING THE OFFER FOR THE SCHOOL AND THE COMMUNITY

Building on a Strong Foundation

As the project moves beyond its initial delivery phase, sustaining the offer within the school will be key. A strong foundation is already in place, with trained staff, established activity, and growing confidence in using the canal as part of the school day. Continuing to embed paddlesport within the curriculum and wider school approach will help ensure students and staff benefit from the programme.

To do this, additional investment in staff capacity, including training additional instructors to ensure delivery can continue is key. There is also opportunity to strengthen inclusivity, identifying ways to engage a wide range of students, particularly those who may face additional barriers to participation.

Additional funding has already enabled investment in infrastructure and facilities, including an outdoor classroom space to support delivery. Alongside trained staff and established activity, this creates a strong base for continued school use and for developing a community paddlesport hub on site.

A Community Paddlesport Hub

Waterside Academy is working with Paddle UK to establish a community paddlesport hub on-site. This will position Waterside as a local access point for the canal, opening opportunities for other schools, local groups, and the wider community to take part in paddlesport and water-based activities. This marks an important transition from project delivery to long-term provision, extending access and resources beyond the school.

CONCLUSION

Waterside Academy: Let's Paddle for Positive Change has demonstrated the value of investing in people, place, and partnership. By building staff skills and confidence, and opening up access to the canal as a safe and usable space, the project has created meaningful opportunities for young people to engage, connect, and grow.

The impacts are visible across the school, from stronger relationships and improved wellbeing to shifts in confidence, behaviour, and engagement. Beyond this, the project has helped to change how the canal is understood and used, repositioning it as a positive and accessible community asset.

With the development of a community paddle hub, the work is now moving beyond a single project. The skills, infrastructure, and partnerships in place create the conditions for sustained impact, supporting ongoing delivery within the school while opening up opportunities to a wider group of users.

Together, these elements are helping to embed long-term change, creating positive ripple effects that extend beyond Waterside Academy and into the wider community.

Learn More

Learn more about Waterside Academy [here](#)

**Canal &
River Trust**
Making life better by water

Learn more about Canal & River Trust [here](#)

GroundsWell
Transforming our cities from the ground up

Learn more about the GroundsWell Community Innovation fund [here](#)

